

ACHIEVING STABILITY IN THE SUPPLY OF FOOD TO THE POPULATION

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Annotation. This article explores the challenges of achieving sustainability in food supply. The article explores the cause of food waste in areas and its environmental negative effects and develops recommendations.

Аннотация. В этой статье исследуются проблемы достижения устойчивости в обеспечении продовольствием. В статье исследуется причина пищевых отходов в регионах и их негативное воздействие на окружающую среду, а также разрабатываются рекомендации.

Keywords: food supply, sustainability, environmental impact, UN, UNEP

Ключевые слова: продовольственное снабжение, устойчивость, воздействие на окружающую среду, ООН, ЮНЕП

Introduction. The increased need for food is becoming the global theme of today. Due to the growing population, the nature of climate change as a result of global warming and the decrease in soil fertility, achieving stability in the production and supply of food is an important task that all countries set before us.

The promised population of 8 billion more than 5 years ago is recorded in this year. And this requires a further increase in food production in its queue. It may be a while difficult for developing countries such as Uzbekistan to achieve sustainable food supply. The need for food can also cause a number of problems for economically developed countries. For example an increase in one real income can increase people's demand for food consumption or change the attitude towards consumption as well.

One of the external factors that causes unfavorable conditions in the production of lean food is that climate change has its own impact on the productivity of the world of Crop Science. Rising temperatures and extreme weather conditions reduce crop yields. There is an increase in demand as a result of a decrease in production.

The increase in prices for food products, which causes difficulties in achieving the stability of the supply of food to the population, is also considered one of today's topical masks. A significant increase in the price of basic foods such as rice, wheat

flour, eggs and sugar in Uzbekistan during 2023 threatened the stability of the food supply.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. Indian economist Amartya Sen highlights the need to ensure social justice and economic opportunities in improving food supply for the population by studying the link between food supply and economic stability in her research on food security and kashkadarya issues. Another economist, Paul Collier, proposes economic policies to reduce fragility and ensure food safety.

Elinor Ostrom mahaly, another scientist who studied social and economic factors in food supply issues, shows the role of communities in the efficient use of resources and ensuring sustainable food supply.

A scientist working at the Institute of Agriculture of Uzbekistan. Khamraev is conducting research on food production and improving their quality. Khamraev's work is aimed at improving the quality of agricultural products and improving the processes of their processing. In addition D.Tashkent, G.Murodova, Sh.Abdullayev also conducted a systematic analysis of the food supply, studying the economic and social factors necessary to provide the population with quality food, and conducting research on this issue and on the development of innovative approaches to consumer protection.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS. At a time when food issues are involving the world's population in the efficient use of resources, some data are informing that certain regions and a certain society are polluting the environment with excess food and waste from these products. A new report presented by the United Nations (UN)Environmental Protection Programme (UNEP) announced that about a third of the world's food would be released into the waste. According to the announcement in it, 30% of the world's existing agricultural land is used for food, of which 1.4 billion hectares are eventually discarded. In addition, it was eventually revealed that 173mrd m³ of water, or 24% of the total water used for agriculture, and 28 million tons of ugit, would be used to grow the food products that are part of the waste heap. According to this global report, more than 900 million tons of food are discarded every year. According to the UNEP food waste index, 17% of consumer-oriented food in shops, homes, and restaurants goes directly to the trash.

In addition, it became known that Uzbekistan is one of the most wasteful countries in the Central Asian region. During the year, it became known that a citizen will throw 91 kilograms of food waste. A study in determining the source of this waste found that food waste coming out of farms would throw away 11 percent, restaurants would throw away 5 percent, and trade networks would throw away 2 percent.

Conclusion. In conclusion ten, we can say that as every citizen, we will have to contribute to the provision of the population with agricultural products, especially food. To achieve this, every citizen must reduce the waste of food products. And this in turn also prevents environmental pollution.

LITERATURE REVIEW

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